

Using silent way method teaching pre elementary level of students

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Annotation: Among the great number of methods for learning English, the silence way method is of special consideration. One of the main principles of this approach is that the teacher performs a passive, “silent” role during an EFL lesson. The foundations of this universal technique were developed by Dr. Caleb Gattegno in the 60s. Having adopted this teaching device first in his classes, Gattegno states that in an English lesson the teacher should not interrupt students and impose his/her point of view on them. Being an unconventional way of teaching, the silence way is supposed to be taught using physical objects in a lesson, for example, tables, rods. The author of the article pays special attention to one of the main goals of this approach development of English-speaking skills. The advantage of the silence way is that the teacher’s language proficiency does not significantly affect the student’s one at a non-philological university.

Key words: speaking, language, communication, pronouncing, silent way
This research aimed to explore whether or not the use of Silent Way Method can improve the students’ speaking ability, to disclose how effective is Silent Way Method in improving students’ speaking ability. The research applied the experimental design and the samples comprised 30 tenth grade students of SMU Negeri 12 Makassar divided into two groups namely experimental class consisted of 15 students class X IPA 3 and control class consisted 15 students class X IPS 3. The

data were collected by using two types of instruments: the speaking test and the questionnaires. The data on the students' speaking ability were analyzed using the descriptive statistics, and the data on the students' questionnaire toward the use of Silent Way Method were analyzed using Likert Scale. The research results revealed that the use of Silent Way Method in teaching speaking had improved the students' speaking ability; and that the students' responses toward the use of Silent Way Method were positive. In fact, the students stated that they found the teaching of speaking more interesting when the Silent Way Method was used to teach them speaking. Thus, the Silent Way Method was effective in improving the students' English-speaking ability; the students also found the method much more interesting when used to teach speaking.

Аннотация: Среди большого количества методов изучения английского языка метод молчания заслуживает особого внимания. Один из основных принципов этого подхода заключается в том, что учитель выполняет пассивную, «молчаливую» роль во время урока английского языка. Основы этой универсальной методики были разработаны доктором Калемом Гаттеньо в 60-х годах. Гаттеньо впервые применил этот метод обучения в своих классах, и он утверждает, что на уроке английского языка учитель не должен прерывать учеников и навязывать им свою точку зрения. Являясь нетрадиционным способом обучения, метод молчания предполагается преподавать с использованием на уроке физических предметов, например, столов, стержней. Особое внимание автор статьи уделяет одной из основных целей данного подхода развитию навыков разговорной речи на английском языке. Преимущество молчаливого пути в том, что в нефилологическом вузе знание языка преподавателем незначительно влияет на знание языка студентом. Ключевые слова: говорение, язык, общение, произношение, silent way.

Nowadays, in learning the second or foreign language, there are four basic skills

that need to be mastered: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Students should be able to use the skills whether in oral or written form. To achieve the goals, teachers have to teach the language skills to their students and improve their English abilities. It is expected that finally, they are able to communicate effectively, orally as well in written form. In other words, mastering speaking skill is very important in learning a language. Speaking is the ability to express opinion, ideas, or thought orally; it consists of producing systematic verbal utterances to convey meaning in order to be understood by the people we are speaking with. Yet, “Celce and Olshtain (2000:165) stated that speaking considers the most difficult skill to acquire since it requires command of both listening comprehension and speech production sub-skills. So, it proves that English is really difficult for students. Speaking is important because people know a language is referred “the speakers” of the language. Many language learners regard speaking ability as the measure of knowing a language. That is why the main purpose of language learning is to develop proficiency in speaking and communicate efficiently. They regard speaking as the most important skill they can acquire and assess their progress in terms of their accomplishments in spoken communication.

Pronunciation teaching is considered very important for the students’ verbal communication. Because the major aim of teaching and learning in any language, according to Harmer (2001), is to make students able to communicate target language (i.e. EFL). To have a good capability of communicating in the context of EFL use, the students are highly advised to learn how to pronounce the EFL sounds correctly to make a good communication. Because the correctness of pronouncing the EFL sounds so merit to be considered to produce a good speaking in the language learning that the students are able to improve both their own inner

criteria for producing the EFL sounds correctly and their ability of doing a good communication. In teaching EFL pronunciation, at the beginning the tutor instructed the students to ‘pay attention’ as his oral introduction and prepared a container consisting of the various color rods. Then he began the pronunciation teaching by picking two red rods, for instance, up out of the container and displaying them to the students, then the tutor paused, and uttered ‘two red rods’ by pronouncing the sound /s/ in the word rods very clearly. Then the students uttered ‘two red rods’. The tutor did the practice again by displaying another rod which was different in number and color to them, four black rods for instance, he paused, and uttered ‘four black rods’ by pronouncing the sound /s/ in the word rods very clearly, and then gave the students a signal by miming to ask them to utter the word that had just

been uttered. The students uttered ‘four black rods’. And after that the tutor silently displayed another rod which was different in number and color to them for example three white rods and urged the students to say the words that had just been displayed by providing the signal. The students did what the tutor had urged i.e: uttering ‘three white rods’. The process of the tutor’s work could be repeated as much as possible until the whole words (such as two red rods, four black rods and three white rods) describing every single of the colored rods became so complete that the students’ EFL pronunciation started to be correct when uttered three white rods for instance, although the students often pronounced the EFL sounds (three white rods for instance) incorrectly before. And the correct pronunciation for the sounds of EFL are

/θri: wa t ra:dz/. Moreover the students would instinctively have knowledge

regarding how to pronounce sound 's' correctly in the word rods i.e.: /ra:dz/ as the final 's' in it has to be pronounced /z/ it is because the word ends voiced sound.

The author of "Teaching Foreign Languages in Schools: The Silent Way", Dr. Caleb Gattegno was famous for his unconventional teaching method and no matter whether it was used in teaching languages, algebra or adult literacy. The educator was known as "the world's greatest teacher" for his dramatically efficient and challenging classes. He created some very flexible techniques that could be effortlessly adopted by students to simplify the grammar and pronunciation complexity of a target language. These teaching techniques turn difficult language-oriented issues into such insights that educator's explanation is not required. A teacher is as silent as possible although a "silent" teacher in the EFL classroom can frequently be misunderstood by students. In this case such educator's behavior is conceived as a pedagogical technique. Dr. Gattegno himself taught various languages including Arabic, Hindi, English, etc. using SW in complete silence from his side.

Successive English language lessons where fundamental SW methodological tools are both fully and partly adopted are of great success among non-philological university students as sound practice is very significant for them. Accordingly, the silent method is highly recommended to be used in teaching a target language although it might seem a bit challenging at the very beginning of the language course. Although being an appropriate technique to a target language teaching, silent way method is still widely criticized by some educators. They believe that making use of physical objects, for example, the color rods during EFL teaching is considered possible and relevant only for young learners whereas the non-philological university students require more advanced and sophisticated approaches. A teacher trainer in the field of teaching English as a foreign language, John Pint states that "teaching a language the Silent Way feels very much like leading a team of investigators on a voyage of

discovery. Like detectives, the students pounce upon each VII Международная научно-практическая конференция piece of the puzzle they find and as they put them all together, they become as confident as their teacher in their mastery of the new language. In fact, it is not unusual for both teacher and students to feel exhilarated after working for six hours during an intensive course". Being a distinguished SW specialist, John Pint in his article "Caleb Gattegno and the silent way" highlights that "whereas a typical teacher might walk into a classroom with a lesson plan in mind and a textbook in hand, a Silent Way teacher might enter the room with a box of colored rods and a very open mind".

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